

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS ON EFFECTIVENESS OF ACOUSTIC MATERIAL AS THERMAL INSULATOR

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ABSTRACT

Sound pollution is big problem now-a-days and it causes many health issues. Soundproofing can be used to mitigate the effect of sound pollution, but it adds to the building cost. However, acoustic materials have low thermal conductivity and they may result in saving due to reduced use of electrical energy for heating/cooling of buildings. In the present work, the effectiveness of a commercially available acoustic material, made of Compressed Wood Fiber Cement Composites with a backing of Anti vibration Pad, as a thermal insulator is experimentally investigated. A CAD model of anti-vibration pad material was developed by scanning it with micro CT, converting grey scale data into binary scale by CTan software and extracting 3D- Model from binary data by using Scan IP software. The CAD model was imported into ANSYS workbench for determining thermal conductivity of the anti-vibration pad, which was experimentally validated. The thermal conductivity of composite material was then calculated by Fourier equation. A comprehensive CAD model of anti-vibration pad, composite material and brick-and-mortar wall was used to simulate the variations in room temperature with ambient temperature for one calendar year. The results show that acoustic insulation material also serves as a thermal insulator keeping the room nearly constant with varying ambient temperature.

KEYWORDS

Acoustic Material, Silent Board, Thermal Insulator, Anti-Vibration Pad, ANSYS

1. INTRODUCTION AND REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Commercial businesses such as cinema halls, convention centers, restaurants etc. use soundproofing material for providing proper ambience to the customers. Many office premises soundproofing play important role for improving work efficiency by increasing their focus and concentration on their work. Further, sound pollution is big problem in cities now-a-days as excessive sound can cause health issues including hypertension, high stress levels, tinnitus, hearing loss, sleep disturbances, and other harmful effects. Therefore, acoustic materials may be used in households also. Though this may add extra cost in building a house but it may also reduce the cost of cooling/heating as acoustic materials have low thermal conductivity. The saving due to reduced use of electrical energy for heating/cooling of homes may offset the additional extra cost of using acoustic insulation material in home.

Manzan et al. reported that the use of internal thermal insulation in existing buildings, reduced energy consumption for heating and cooling. In mostly cases of Historical buildings due to local regulations use of internal insulation is the only option as compare to external insulation [1]. Skotnicova et al. Presented the result due to thermal Performance on different wall material may be calculated by numerical simulation as well as experimental measurement [2]. Fiedler et al.

described the thermal finite element analysis of cellular aluminum with non-uniform pore structures. Finite element models were produced with computed tomography images. A meshing algorithm was used where each finite element corresponds to CT voxels [3]. Cnudde and Boone presented a review of high-resolution X-ray computed tomography in geosciences. The main advantages of technique was the fact that it is a non-destructive characterization technique which allows 4D monitoring of internal structural changes at resolutions down to a few hundred nanometers [4]. Arora and Dhami presented the use of ANSYS for static analysis of gear assembly of a robot manipulator. Four different material were simulated for maximum stress, strain and the most suitable material is recommended for used [5].

2. OBJECTIVES

Objective of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of commercially available acoustic material as a thermal insulator. A commercially available acoustic material made of Compressed Wood Fiber Cement Composites with a backing of Anti vibration Pad was used in the present work.

3. ACOUSTIC MATERIAL USED

Silent boards of thickness 14mm, 16mm, 18mm and 22mm and made of Compressed Wood Fiber Cement Composites with a backing of Anti vibration Pad are manufactured by M/S Kool Pack & Allied Industries, Dharampur, Himachal Pradesh. In the present work, a 16 mm thick silent board of brand name "Himalayan Acoustics" manufactured by M/S Kool Pack & Allied Industries, Dharampur, Himachal Pradesh, was used in the present work. The silent board is an acoustic material used in auditorium, seminar and cinema halls etc. This silent board has a low thermal conductivity of 0.0795 W/mk [6], due to which it may be used to keep the room insulated from environment temperature variation.

4. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

A CAD model of the silent board mounted on a brick-and-mortar wall cemented on both sides was developed and used for simulating the temperature on one side of the wall with the other side exposed to different temperatures. The various models of silent boards have Compressed Wood Fiber Cement Composite and Anti vibration Pad portions of varying thickness. Therefore, to make a CAD model which could be used for thermal modeling of various silent boards, it was necessary to determine the thermal conductivity of Compressed Wood Fiber Cement Composite and Anti vibration Pad portions individually.

Thermal conductivity of the anti-vibration pad was determined experimentally as well as through Finite Element Analysis. The thermal conductivity of the composite board was calculated by subtracting the anti-vibration pad thermal conductivity from the overall thermal conductivity provided by the manufacture.

4.1. Thermal Conductivity by Experimental Method

KD2 pro was used to measure the thermal conductivity of anti-vibration pad using single needle sensor, Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Measurement of Thermal Conductivity of Anti-vibration pad Material

Most of the cases the temperature of the sample is different than the needle temperature which is not the favorable condition, then needle temperature equilibrate with ambient temperature. [7]. The thermal conductivity of the anti-vibration pad was found to be $0.03 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$ at 23.3°C .

4.2. Determination of Thermal Conductivity by Finite Elemental Analysis

The thermal conductivity in steady state heat transfer was simulated by Finite Element Analysis (FEA) method [8], which was carried out following the steps shown in Fig 2.

Figure 2: Steps in Modeling Anti-Vibration Pad

Samples were scanned in Skyscan 1173 X-ray micro-computer tomography (μCT) machine. The multiple X-ray shadow projection images were recorded at different angular positions of the sample [8]. From the projection images, a cubic volume corresponding to a physical side length of 2.43 mm was reconstructed using modified Feldkamp cone beam software (NRecon, SKYSCAN). The reconstructed 3-D images have an isotropic resolution of $12.15 \mu\text{m}$, resulting in 200 images of 200×200 pixels, which is a considerable quantity of volumetric data for processing. From the projection images, cubic volumes were reconstructed using modified

Feldkamp cone beam software (NRecon, SKYSCAN). The reconstructed 3D images of Antivibration pad were grey scale images and have an isotropic resolution of 12.15 μm , resulting in 200 images of 200 x 200 pixels.

Anti-vibration pad material was taken and micro-CT was performed on it. Stack of images were obtained from micro-CT. Binary data was extracted from these stack of images with the help of CTan software. It gave the location of material and pores in binary format. Conversion into binary format was done because the software further understands binary format only.

SCAN IP software was used for obtaining 3D model of the region of interest chosen from the binary data. The binary data that was extracted was processed in SCAN IP. The green color in the picture symbolizes the non-connected part and the red one depicts the connected part. Nonconnected part was subtracted because in simulations, when displacement is given, there will be no reaction from that part due to absence of proper base. Fig 3 represent the post treatment 3D structure of sample.

Figure 3: Post Treatment 3D Structure of Sample

The 3D model generated in Scan IP was imported in ANSYS software and boundary condition in the form of temperature on both side of the anti-vibration pad material were applied as shown in Fig.4

Figure 4: Boundary conditions for FEA model

The heat flux through the anti-vibration pad material was simulated by varying the number of iterations and it was observed that the results were saturated for 30 iterations. The average heat flux was taken to be 0.3454 w/m² [3]. Using the Heat flux value, the boundary condition and the thickness of the anti-vibration pad material was obtained as 0.029 W/mK from Fourier equation. Thus, the variation in thermal conductivity of anti-vibration pad material determined experimentally (0.03 W/mK) and by simulation (0.029) was 3.3% only which is negligible. Therefore, the model of the anti-vibration pad material obtained using microcomputer tomography and Scan I.P software was validated.

5. EFFECTIVENESS OF ACOUSTIC MATERIAL AS THERMAL INSULATOR

Simulations were carried out to estimate the effect of acoustic material as a thermal insulator in a building. A comprehensive CAD model of anti-vibration pad, composite material and brick-and-mortar wall cemented on both sides was made in Ansys modeler. Simulations were carried out by exploring one side of the wall to the minimum and maximum ambient temperature values for full calendar year, Table 1, and observing the temperature on the other side of the wall, without and with the Acoustic material.

Table 1: Maximum and Minimum Temperature in 2018 [9]

		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Temperature (°C)	Minimum	6.1	8.3	13.4	18.9	23.1	25.4	23.9	23.3	21.8	17	10.5	6.7
	Maximum	20.4	23.1	28.4	34.5	38.3	38.6	34	32.7	33.1	31.8	27.3	22.1

Simulations were carried out by considering initial temperature on the unexposed side of the wall to be 24°C and recording the temperature after 8 hours of simulation time. In this manner total of 48 simulations were carried -24 without the acoustic material and 24 with the acoustic material. Further out of 24 simulations, 12 were carried out by considering the minimum temperature and other 12 by considering the maximum temperature on the exposed side of the wall. The simulation results for room temperature without and with acoustic material for minimum ambient temperature during the year 2018 are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Room Temperature without and with Acoustic Material for Minimum Ambient Temperature in 2018

The magnitude of variation in room temperature during a year from baseline temperature of 24°C for minimum ambient temperature is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Magnitude of Room Temperature Variation for Minimum Ambient Temperature

Month	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Magnitude of Variation in Room Temperature (°C) (For Mean Room Temperature of 24°C)	
		Without Acoustic Material	With Acoustic Material
Jan	6.1	2.963	0.552
Feb	8.3	2.599	0.484
Mar	13.4	1.754	0.327
Apr	18.9	0.844	0.157
May	23.1	0.149	0.028
Jun	25.4	0.232	0.043
Jul	23.9	0.1	0.017
Aug	23.3	0.7	0.116
Sep	21.8	2.2	0.364
Oct	17	1.159	0.216
Nov	10.5	2.234	0.416
Dec	6.7	2.863	0.533
Average Variation:		1.483083	0.271083

It is observed that the maximum variation in room temperature from baseline temperature occurs in winters and minimum variation occurs in summer. The average variation from baseline temperature without acoustic material is 447.10% as compared to that with acoustic material.

The simulation results for room temperature without and with acoustic material for maximum ambient temperature during the year 2018 are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Room Temperature without and with Acoustic Material for Minimum Ambient Temperature in 2018

The magnitude of variation in room temperature during a year from baseline temperature of 24°C for maximum ambient temperature is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Magnitude of Room Temperature Variation for Maximum Ambient Temperature

Month	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Magnitude of Variation in Room Temperature (°C) (For Mean Room Temperature of 24°C)	
		Without Acoustic Material	With Acoustic Material
Jan	20.4	0.596	0.111
Feb	23.1	0.149	0.028
Mar	28.4	0.728	.136
Apr	34.5	1.738	.324
May	38.3	2.367	.441
Jun	38.6	2.417	.45
Jul	34	1.655	.308
Aug	32.7	1.44	.268
Sep	33.1	1.506	.28
Oct	31.8	1.291	.24
Nov	27.3	.546	.102
Dec	22.1	.314	0.059
Average Variation:		1.228917	0.228917

It is observed that the maximum variation in room temperature from baseline temperature occurs in summers and minimum variation occurs in winters. The average variation from baseline temperature without acoustic material is 436.84% as compared to that with acoustic material. Therefore, without acoustic material the variation in temperature is substantial as compare to that with acoustic material through the year.

The minimum and maximum room temperatures without and with acoustic material for one calendar year is shown in Table 4, for a mean room temperature of 24°C.

Table 4: Actual Room Temperature Without and With Acoustic Material

Month	Without Acoustic Material		With Acoustic Material	
	Minimum (°C)	Maximum (°C)	Minimum (°C)	Maximum (°C)
Jan	21.04	23.40	23.45	23.89
Feb	21.40	23.85	23.52	23.97
Mar	22.25	24.73	23.67	24.14
Apr	23.16	25.74	23.84	24.32
May	23.85	26.37	23.97	24.44
Jun	24.23	26.42	24.04	24.45
Jul	23.90	25.66	23.98	24.31
Aug	23.30	25.44	23.88	24.27
Sep	21.80	25.51	23.64	24.28
Oct	22.84	25.29	23.78	24.24
Nov	21.77	24.55	23.58	24.10

Dec	21.14	23.69	23.47	23.94
Average	22.56	25.05	23.74	24.20

The average room temperature for a complete calendar year varies from mean room temperature of 24°C by 5.2% when acoustic material is not used, whereas the variation is only 0.95% when acoustic material is used. Therefore, it may be stated that the acoustic material, whose primary purpose is sound insulation, also serves as a thermal insulator thereby saving energy in keeping the room at a nominal temperature.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Sound pollution causes many health issues and its ill-effects mitigated by soundproofing. The additional costs involved in soundproofing a building may be offset to some extent by savings due to reduced use of electrical energy for heating/cooling of buildings, as acoustic materials have low thermal conductivity. In the present work, the effectiveness of a commercially available acoustic material, made of Compressed Wood Fiber Cement Composites with a backing of Anti vibration Pad, as a thermal insulator was investigated. A comprehensive CAD model of acoustic insulation material and brick-and-mortar wall was used to simulate the variations in room temperature, initially at 24°C, with changing ambient temperature over a period of one calendar year. The results show that the average room temperature varies from mean room temperature by 5.2% when acoustic material is not used, whereas the variation is only 0.95% when acoustic material is used.

REFERENCES

- [1] Marco Manzan, Ezio Zandegiacomo De Zorzi, Walter Lorenzi, *Numerical simulation and sensitivity analysis of a steel framed internal insulation system*, J. Energy and Buildings, Elsevier, vol 158(2018) pp 1703–1710.
- [2] Iveta Skotnicova, Zdenek Galda, Petra Tymova, Lenka Lausova, *Experimental Measurement and Numerical Simulation of Dynamic Thermal Performance of External Timber Frame Wall*, J. Advanced Materials Research, Trans Tech Publication, Vol 899 (2014) pp 126-130.
- [3] T. Fiedler, E. Solórzano, F. Garcia-Moreno, A. Öchsner, I.V. Belova, G.E. Murch, *Computed tomography based finite element analysis of the thermal properties of cellular aluminium*, Wiley 2009.
- [4] V Cnudde, M.N. Boone, *High-resolution X-ray computed tomography in geosciences: A review of the current technology and applications*, J. Earth-Science Reviews(2013), Elsevier.
- [5] Rahul Arora and S.S Dhami, *Finite Element Analysis and Multibody Dynamics of 6-Dof Industrial Robot*, International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development (IJMPERD), ISSN (P): 2249-6890; ISSN (E): 2249-8001, Vol. 7, 1-12, Issue 5, Oct 2017.
- [6] www.himalyanacoustics.com
- [7] Neil Lockmuller, John Redgrove, L Kubicar, *Measurement of thermal conductivity with the needle probe*, High Temperatures-High Pressures, 2003/2004, volume 35/36, pages 127- 138
- [8] Chaman Chandel, Praveen K. Srivastava, P.Mahajan. "Micromechanical analysis of deformation of snow using X-ray tomography", Cold Regions Science and Technology, 2014
- [9] <https://www.weather-atlas.com/en/india/chandigarh-weather>.